

Solstice celebrations

Pagan origins – the Christian Church – Freemasonry

Poems for the solstices – Reflections – Poem for the solstice song

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Extract

This is a work of research, but also of Masonic experience, poetry and ritual readings. This presentation consists of asking questions that the research article will attempt to answer.

What are the origins of the solstice festival? What are the links between solstice festivals and the Church?

Why are there two Saint Johns? What are the symbolic elements of the Saint John's Day celebrations? What are the symbolic values in Freemasonry? What are the links between the essential values highlighted in this article concerning solstice celebrations, the four elements and V.I.T.R.I.O.L.?

What are the relationships between Brotherhood, Knowledge, Nature and the Bonfires of Saint John in Freemasonry?

This work presents two poems: the first concerns the Feast of Saint John in winter and the second concerns the Feast of Saint John in summer.

Finally, this research article concludes with a nine-point reflection on 'Knowledge' in Freemasonry.

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1. Pagan sources of solstice celebrations

Solstices occur when one of the Earth's poles reaches its maximum inclination relative to the sun. Solstice celebrations have pagan origins. These celebrations date back so far in time that it is difficult to pinpoint their origins. The focus of this research paper is on the solstice celebrations of Freemasonry.

The longest days in the Northern Hemisphere are between 21 June and 24 June, when the sun warms the earth with maximum intensity. It is therefore during this short period that the solstice festival takes place. The same is true of the winter solstice festival, but then the sun fades and the nights are longer. The Gregorian calendar sets the solstice festival on 24 June. Astronomy allows us to determine the longest day in summer and the longest night in winter and thus set the two solstice festivals.

We know that even in Neolithic times, festivals related to the sun and light were celebrated. For some European peoples at that time, the solstices symbolized the death and rebirth of the sun. In Europe? Think of the megalithic site of Stonehenge, built in stages between 3000 and 1100 BC near Salisbury in England. Stonehenge is circular in shape and appears to have been built as a place of worship to worship the sun. Other theories exist about Stonehenge: some claim that the site was a place of healing, others that it was a giant musical instrument, and still others that it was an ancient crystal ball. Apart from the more far-fetched theories, in concrete terms, Stonehenge is a monument with two concentric circles aligned with the sunset on the winter solstice.

The solstices were already celebrated by the Egyptians, Romans and elsewhere. The god Ra was the creator sun god of the Egyptians and was considered the father of all gods. The summer solstice was celebrated outdoors with a bonfire, while the winter solstice was celebrated indoors with a domestic fire. Among the Romans, as among the Egyptians, the summer solstice was associated with fertility and abundance.

Paganism has left traces in the Christian religion. For example, the sun disc of the Egyptian god became the halo of saints. The Christian summer festival of Saint John's Day was the solstice festival of Litha among the Celts (as opposed to Yule, for the winter solstice). Celtic festivals inspired the Christian Church in two ways: the bonfires of St. John's Day symbolized the power of light (bonfires) and the ritual of purification (with water from the River Jordan by John the Baptist, symbolism adopted by the Church). Similarly, while in paganism nature was linked to abundant harvests in summer, in the Christian church nature became a symbol of creation by the Creator and, in a subtle way, the Church linked the Eucharist to bread and wine (the body and blood of Christ).

The sun god Mithra had long been called "Son of God and Light of the World." His birth was celebrated on 25 December, which was also the birthday of Osiris, the " " of Adonis and Dionysus. The cult of Mithra was active in the second century BC. Christianity used elements

of the cult of Mithra to construct the Christian religion. Indeed, there are traces of similarities between the two religions. For example, there is a similarity between the death of Jesus and that of Mithra. The latter was buried in a rocky cave and rose again three days later.

Another similarity used to construct the Christian religion concerns the analogy between the Three Wise Men visiting the newborn Jesus and Krishna, who also received gifts of gold, frankincense and myrrh. Even Sunday, the weekly holy day, was modelled on that of the pagans, as Christians originally honoured the Jewish Sabbath. It was the Roman Emperor Constantine I who moved the day to 'Sunday' to coincide with the celebration of the god Mithra, the sun god.

The solstice festival also existed in other interesting cultures. For example, the Celts organized large festivals at the summer solstice, as it was necessary to win the favour of the gods to ensure the survival of mankind. The pre-Christian festival of Yule was celebrated by Germanic peoples. This festival was associated with the tradition of the Yule log. It is also worth noting that the festive rituals of Yule were incorporated into the famous Christmas log. Yule was the opposite of Litha, which was celebrated in summer.

For the summer solstice, fires were lit in the hope of good harvests and the ashes were scattered in the fields. People gave thanks to the earth, which had been fertilized with seeds that had become plants and fruits ripened by the sun. It was therefore a tribute to nature, whose cycles were known to the people of the earth. The light generated by the fire had a symbolic connection with the sun; this light was believed to be capable of driving away demons. The Phoenicians and Syrians organized large festivals to honour the god of abundance, vegetation and livestock, the source of human survival.

Beliefs and superstitions existed, such as the property of ashes, which were scattered on the ground to protect crops from lightning. On a more romantic note, lovers would jump over the fire so that their love would last all year long.

Gradually, the winter solstice came to symbolize the hope of the return of light through regeneration. On a more symbolic level, it represented the ability of nature and man, both part of the macrocosm, to regain regenerative energy through inner forces. Why?

Because the external environment (winter) was hostile. The winter solstice therefore symbolizes the blossoming of inner light, which is the source of life. The symbolism of the winter solstice marks the return of the hoped-for light after the numbness caused by the cold of the long nights. It was therefore already a rebirth.

1.1 The days, the planets, the gods and the sun

It is interesting to note the meaning of the word "Sunday" in French, which means "day of the Lord" (*dies domingo* in Christian Latin, whereas in classical Latin, Sunday was called "*dies solis*," meaning "day of the sun"). In other languages, there are interesting meanings that can be observed. For example, Sunday in English means "day of the sun", Zondag in Dutch, Sonntag in German, Söndag in Swedish, Vasárnap in Hungarian, a word that comes from the Slavic "Voskresenje", meaning "Resurrection", but "nap" has a double meaning, depending on the context: "day" or "sun"; thus, "Vasárnap is the literal equivalent of "Resurrection of the Sun". Domenica in Italian, Domingo in Spanish, Niedziela in Polish, which comes from Old Slavic and literally means "The day when nothing is done", Pazar in Turkish, which means both Sunday and "market". A peculiarity of Russian: the etymology of the word "Sunday" is "resurrection".

In India, "Sunday" is "Ravivaar", "Ravi" meaning "Sun" and "Vaar" meaning "Day", so "Day of the Sun". The word "Sunday" is a passage from the Roman calendar, based on the planets in the Christian calendar, which honours the "Day of the Lord". In fact, celestial bodies formed the days of the week. For example, in French: Monday (*Lune* or *Luna*, *Lunaes dies* in Latin), Tuesday (*Mars*, or *Martius*, *Martis dies* in Latin), Wednesday (*Mercure*, or *Mercurius*, *Mercurii dies* in Latin), Thursday (*Jupiter*, or *Joviter*, whose genitive is *Jovis* in Latin), Friday (*Venus*, or *Veneris*, *Veneris dies*). For the Romans, the days of the week were therefore dedicated to gods. For example, Venus was the god of love; Jupiter was the king of the gods, the god of the sky (thunder, thunder) and protector of Rome, "Mercury" was the god of commerce, messenger of the other gods and travellers, "Mars" was the god of war and father of Romulus and Remus, founders of Rome, "Moon" was the goddess of the full moon, associated with the feminine, goddess of beauty, love and fertility.

However, as for "Saturday", if this word was called "*Saturnus, dies Saturni*" (the day of Saturn) in Latin, the Church Christianized the day "Saturday" by replacing its meaning with "day of the Sabbath" in Latin (*Sabbati dies*). For the Romans, Saturn was the god of time and agriculture, associated with fertility and harvests, but also the god of wealth. Sunday as a day of rest has existed since Emperor Constantine I made it "the day of the sun" in honour of the unconquered sun on 7th March 321.

It should be noted that in Ancient Greece, there were also gods who had specific qualities and roles. The Romans largely appropriated the Greek gods and renamed them. For example, Jupiter = Zeus, Mars = Ares, Moon = Selene (Selê'nê), Mercury = Hermes, Venus = Aphrodite.

Many languages have retained the meaning "Day of the Sun," but in other languages, such as Russian and Turkish, the etymology of the last day of the week is different. Many Native American nations used lunar and solar cycles () to count time and mark passages, but in practice, there were no names specifying the days of the week. Astronomical observation was used for lunar and solar calendars.

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From pagan solstice celebrations, we can highlight a few important elements:

- Fire, which is an element that purifies and warms, linked to the sun
- Light, which illuminates thanks to the sun and can protect against darkness and demons
- Knowledge: the crafts of the land, culture, the seasons, the cycles of the year, etc.
- The convivial and social joy generated by solstice celebrations (music, dancing, feasting, etc.).
- For the Greeks and Romans, the gods were part of everyday life and played important roles, including during festivals.

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2. The two Saint Johns: winter and summer, in Freemasonry

The word solstice comes from the Latin sol, meaning sun, and sistere, meaning to stop, referring to the azimuth of the Sun at sunrise and sunset, as it appears to remain stationary for a few days at these times of the year.

Masonic tradition is based on symbolism, which is the means of transmission. Tradition induces transmission.

As a result, Freemasonry is both "past, present and future", because every man carries within him the experience of previous generations. The present builds on experience, and the future allows us to understand the past and the present, while offering the possibility of going further. From a Masonic point of view, this is one of the reasons why we talk about the "Masonic journey".

In Freemasonry, the solstice celebrations (winter and summer) have a very symbolic meaning. In lodges, the feast of Saint John's Day takes place around 24th December, depending on each lodge's calendar, although lodges of the same obedience always try to set a common date. The same applies to the summer solstice, which is celebrated around 24th June each year.

The difference between Saint John's Day in winter and Saint John's Day in summer lies mainly in the time of year when they are celebrated and their significance. The winter solstice celebrates the victory of day over night, while the summer solstice celebrates the longest day and therefore the shortest night.

Midsummer, usually celebrated on 24th June, is a very popular festival in several countries, particularly in France, due to its connection with the summer solstice. It is a festival that celebrates light and nature, and is often accompanied by bonfires, dancing and traditions related to fertility and rebirth.

Saint John's Day in winter, celebrated around 24th December, marks the end of a cycle, but also the beginning of a new year, with celebrations also linked to Christmas and focused on family, sharing, human warmth, renewal and spirituality. In contrast, Midsummer's Day is a summer festival celebrating light and nature, revelry and the joys that the earth offers us.

During a Masonic solstice celebration, the ritual refers extensively to 'Janus'. Who is Janus and why do Freemasons use him? Janus is the Roman god of beginnings and endings, of passage and doors. He is depicted with two faces, one looking towards the past and the other towards the future. Janus was worshipped as the god of origins and things.

The god of doors was essential to Rome, as the people were very superstitious and there was a ritual before the Roman legions went into battle and when they returned, cheered by the crowd.

Janus was feared and considered the guardian of the heavenly gates. He held the keys to the stages of the path to Light, symbolizing the immortality of the spirit. The northern gates of Rome represented the gates of Hell, and the southern gates were called the gates of Heaven. It

is interesting to note that with the Christianization of Rome, Janus was replaced by Saint John the Baptist and Saint John the Evangelist. In general, the Church does not like to highlight pagan sources that have been adopted and transformed by the Church.

Janus is therefore the image of the passage from one world to another, which occurs precisely at the winter solstice and the summer solstice. There are close links between the past and the present; this is undoubtedly why we can see "Janus with two heads on a Roman coin. Janus therefore knows the past and projects the things of life into the future. As a result, Janus had the power to master the science of the past and the future. As "Janus" is the beginning, he is therefore the "god of the beginning" at the Winter Solstice. The month of Janus corresponds to "Januaris" (January). As a sun god, he presided over the "Matutinus Pater", i.e. the rising of the sun.

The "Beginning" implies light, which is undoubtedly why the Romans attributed an essential role to it in the creation of the world. It was considered the god of gods, "Janus Pater".

We must not forget the theory of René Guénon, a Freemason (1886-1951), concerning the "Lesser Mysteries" and the "Greater Mysteries". The "Lesser Mysteries" concern man, his initiation through the development of his faculties in order to achieve the restoration of the "primordial state". In Freemasonry, the Summer Solstice is celebrated, which corresponds to the gateway for mankind. The Summer Solstice is represented by Saint John the Baptist, symbolizing renewal and light through initiation. For Christians, baptism offers mankind a new life.

The "Great Mysteries" represent the gateway to the gods. They lead to "Final Deliverance" and "Supreme Identity." Such a process can only take place through "supra-individual" states, which are therefore non-human. For him, there are three worlds, the world of manifestation having three dimensions. The first dimension is gross or a corporeal manifestation; the second dimension is subtle or a psychic manifestation; and the third dimension is spiritual or an informal manifestation. Guénon is an important figure for Freemasons. In Switzerland, for example, there is a lodge named after him: Loge maçonnique René Guénon, no. 76, in the Orient of Lausanne. This lodge is part of the Grande Loge Suisse Alpina, the main regular Masonic obedience founded in 1844 and with more than 3,500 members.

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Solstice ritual, Respectable Lodge "France", Modern French Rite, GLSH

2.1 Winter Saint John's Day

Saint John's Day, celebrated between 21 and 26th December, marks the longest night and the shortest day of the year. As already mentioned, it marks the renewal of light and the beginning of the next cycle. Symbolically, it represents the gradual victory of light over darkness. The fire lit and passed from Brother to Brother also symbolizes sharing and the warmth of life, which gradually takes its place in a new cycle of nature.

For Freemasons, it is a symbolic moment of rebirth and purification. It is also the adoption of ancient rites that celebrated the passage from darkness to light. In a way, with a renewal, we pass from death back to life and thus regain balance on the pendulum of life. Renewal is spiritual in nature, inviting the Mason to let his ignorance die in order to allow knowledge to be resurrected.

Thus, as in pagan festivals, the symbols of "Fire", "Light" and "Knowledge" are important, but with a different, more symbolic spiritual dimension. To this symbolism in , another is added: "brotherhood", where conviviality and joyful feasting are somewhat reminiscent of the joy of the solstice celebrations of the pagan festivals, but once again with a different depth of spirit.

As light grows with each passing day, symbolically, light brings knowledge that grows through introspection and the sharing of knowledge. For Freemasons, this is a quest for truth, knowing, however, that the truth, which could be represented by a shining celestial body, can never be attained, but only approached.

The Masonic ritual of the solstice celebration is an emotionally charged moment that aims to strengthen the fraternal bonds between members, while reminding them of the importance of

inner light to illuminate their path in life. The message of the winter solstice is therefore a message of hope. The solstice celebration tends to strengthen the bonds between the brothers, recalling in the ritual the values of light, wisdom and brotherhood that are at the heart of Masonry. During the ceremony and the fraternal agape, there are often exchanges of fraternal greetings and the wish that each Brother may progress in the Royal Art. Winter Saint John's Day is represented by Saint John the Evangelist, whose Prologue and Apocalypse are important texts. Winter Saint John's Day is the gateway to the Great Mysteries, that is, the gateway to the gods and not to men.

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2.2 Poem for Saint John's Day in winter

Saint John's Day in Winter

In the shadow of the frosty night
A celebration appears in the veiled lights
Hope lives in a song of light
To chase away the cold dust

The Brothers are there, despite the frost
Around eternal dreams
The stars shine on every stone
Illuminating our sincere wishes.

Words are carried by the wind
Stories of yesteryear, of fire and time
A peaceful celebration, memories
Of human warmth, to start anew

In the winter snow, the celebration is reborn,
Our inner flame, offering Peace

Winter Saint John's Day, filled with hope
Unites us in love and knowledge.

Ferenc Sebök, 2005

2.3 Midsummer and its virtues

The Feast of Saint John the Baptist, celebrated by Freemasons between 21 and 26 June, depending on the calendar, is linked to Saint John the Baptist, who baptized Jesus and prepared his way as a saviour and the idea of redemption. The symbolism of "Light" is important because it invites the Mason to look within himself to seek a little light in order to "make progress in Freemasonry" (REAA ritual).

The two Saint John's Day celebrations are also represented by the two-headed god Janus, with one head looking to the past and the other to the future, reminiscent of a Roman coin depicting Janus. Midsummer Day also has the symbols of light, nature, knowledge and brotherhood.

Summer Saint John's Day gives Masons the opportunity to engage in introspection, like the Profane in the Cabinet of Reflection, in order to progress in their quest for light and knowledge. Nature is represented by elements such as wheat, wine, oil and incense. These are elements used in the erection of the Columns of a New Lodge.

Light also symbolizes purification and the search for truth, even if this is like an unattainable star. This light is the opposite of darkness. Is not the goal of the Mason to know himself better so that he can "get rid of his metals in the Lodge", "overcome his passions and make new progress in Freemasonry" (REAA ritual)? I cannot help but make the connection between the light that leads to knowledge and the link between light and the cardinal virtues (prudence, justice, strength and temperance), as well as the theological virtues (hope, faith and charity).

Prudence implies the discernment and wisdom of King Solomon. Justice reminds us of the importance of being fair and honest. Strength, linked to light and the sun, is also linked to courage and perseverance, meanwhile, is linked to the ability to control one's passions and act with moderation.

The theological virtues are Christian in essence, but for Freemasons, this also means that faith is necessary to believe in what we do, in what we choose, and in the path of the Royal Art that we have decided to follow. For the Christian Church, faith is linked to the Creator, who is a revealed God in whom the believer has complete trust.

Hope is linked to the perfectibility of man, the hope of finding more light in his quest. Christian hope, on the other hand, is linked to the promise of salvation and eternal life. Charity in Masonry is synonymous with brotherly love and mutual aid. In the AASR ritual, we read the following:

"I pledge to love my brothers... to help them..."

For Christians, charity represents God's unconditional and selfless love: "God is love", but it is also selfless love for one's neighbour. These differences between the Christian view of virtues and the view of Freemasons lead to the essential conclusion that religion is "dogmatic" and Freemasonry is "adogmatic".

The First Principle of the Constitution of the Regular Grand Lodge of Belgium states that it is necessary to believe in God, the Great Architect of the Universe, but members are free to choose their own representation of the Supreme Being.

Here is a precise extract from the said Constitution:

"Freemasonry affirms the existence of God, the Supreme Being, whom it designates as the Great Architect of the Universe... Freemasonry does not define the Supreme Being and leaves everyone free to conceive of Him as they wish."

Compared to Anderson's Constitutions, where the concept of God is a revealed God, the Constitution creates ambiguity by stating that the concept of God is left to the discretion of each individual. Obviously, the 18th century is not the 21st century: mentalities have changed, as have "behavioural trends." The same is true, for example, with regard to the concepts of freedom, probity, and morality (good morals).

Indeed, people's perceptions of these three concepts have changed and are no longer the same as they were at the time. This is one of the reasons why some Freemasons today, and some Obediences, may consider that the Constitutions of Anderson, a Presbyterian minister by profession, have become relics that are at least partially out of touch with our reality in the 21st century. The same applies to the Feast of St. John: beliefs have changed, perceptions have changed, and Freemasonry has given it a different symbolism from that of paganism or the Church. As a result, Freemasonry must also be able to adapt with regard to the concepts of liberty, equality, fraternity, probity, good morals, etc.

Let us take two concrete examples. The concept of "good morals" has changed according to civilizations (ancient Greece, the Romans, the Middle Ages, the Age of Enlightenment, when the Church was all-powerful and had total influence over the people, etc.). The same is true of the concepts of freedom; freedom concerned the notable, those who could vote, as opposed to beggars, serfs, and slaves.

The first change in Freemasonry occurred when Freemasonry moved from operative to speculative, integrating people who were not tradesmen (the nobility).

The second change was that the bourgeoisie were able to join Freemasonry because they were wealthy.

The third change came during the industrial period of modern times, with the social movements of the late 19th century, when Freemasonry became "democratized," opening the door to those who were called the "low earners."

The fourth change took place during the disputes over the concept of God (late 19th century, early 20th century), with a split between atheist Masons who rejected “God” and those who wanted to remain faithful to the ancient “Landmarks.”

The fifth change has been taking place since the 1990s, with globalization and the emergence of “wokism,” challenging the established “moral order.” These changes have shaken people's views on the “theological and cardinal virtues.”

The importance of "nature" linked to St. John's Day is closely related to brotherly love and is manifested in Freemasonry, in particular through the sharing of bread and wine. Bread comes from wheat and wine from the vine. Bread and wine are symbolically linked to the earth, which nourishes us and provides two essential elements: food and drink. For Christians, is this not symbolically the body of Christ and the blood shed for us? This symbolism of the cross is found in Freemasonry in the 18th degree Rose+Croix (REAA), with the Brother carrying the mystical lamb.

Man himself is an element of nature, a microcosmic entity within the macrocosmic universe of which he is a part.

2.4 Poem for St John's Day

After winter, Midsummer's Day lights up
The fires dance, the night burns
Hearts everywhere unfold,
In the warmth of celebration and joy

The flames crackle, telling stories
Traditions and memories filled with glory
Songs rise, carried by a breeze
Everything lights up in an indescribable surprise

The Brothers are reunited in harmony
Sharing laughter and sweet company
Under the starry sky, the night becomes magical
Celebrating light, life, poetry

Ferenc Sebök, 2005

3. The Church's appropriation of the Feast of St. John

Many elements of the Catholic ritual, such as the mitre and the altar, originate from paganism. The same is true of the doxology (formulas of praise to God) and the Eucharist, which is one of the three sacraments of Christian initiation using bread and wine: "Do this in memory of me!". In the Catholic religion, the host replaces the bread used by Protestants.

The Catholic Mass was also modelled on the rituals of Mithra. The appearance of the first saints and martyrs dates back to the time of Emperor Constantine I.

In the fourth century AD, it is likely that the Catholic Church wanted to align pagan traditions with religious holidays. Emperor Constantine ¹ (272-337) achieved a remarkable feat by forcing an entire pagan people to convert to Christianity through a clever fusion of pagan dates, rituals, and symbols into the emerging Christian tradition. The Edict of Milan in 313, signed by Constantine and Licinius (his co-emperor, whom he would later get rid of at the Battle of Adrianople in 324), legalized Christianity and put an end to the persecution of Christians. Constantine I succeeded in creating a hybrid religion that could be assimilated by all his subjects. Through the Edict of Milan, only one religion was recognized: Christianity. The tone was set by Constantine I, who had rid himself of the emperors Maxentius (in 312 at the Battle of Milvian Bridge) and Licinius (at the Battle of Adrianople in 324): "One God and one Emperor".

Constantine was a major emperor who succeeded in unifying the weakened Roman Empire. He put an end to the persecution of Christians and the conflicts of the Eastern churches by convening the First Council of Nicaea in 325, and in 330 he founded Constantinople, which bears his name. Constantine became one of the saints of the Orthodox Church, which considers him, "equal to the Apostles". In the Catholic Church, he is known as "Constantine the Great".

The story of Constantine is also interesting in the Masonic world, as the character exists in a "Side Degree" (an auxiliary order), a military order called the "Red Cross of Constantine". One must be a Master Mason and be co-opted to enter the first degree of the Order called "Knight of the Red Cross of Constantine."

In Catholicism, there are seven sacraments: baptism, confirmation, Eucharist, penance (or reconciliation), anointing of the sick and extreme unction for the dying, ordination (of priests) and marriage. It should be noted that among Protestants, there are only two sacraments: baptism and the Holy Communion (Eucharist), as these two sacraments were instituted by Jesus Christ. These two sacraments are mentioned in the Gospels, but not the others.

For its part, the Christian Church in the Middle Ages did not hesitate to appropriate the solstice festivals for very specific reasons related to the conversion of the population. Indeed, deeply rooted beliefs are always very difficult to change, as people resist change. The easy solution was therefore, on the one hand, to appropriate a pagan festival, removing elements

that were unacceptable to the Church because they were contrary to the prevailing dogma, and on the other hand, to incorporate a sacred religious character, thus reinforcing the magnificence of the transformed festival. For the most credulous populations of the time, introducing a "mystery" also added value, thereby making the festival "sacred". This operation took a long time, of course, before the Christian festival of Saint John became omnipresent in people's minds as a sacred ritual at the end of each cycle.

By adding the Christian theological values (Hope, Faith, Charity), the Church offered a message of hope for all: "God is Love and sent his Son, Christ, to save the world." The culmination of this is the Last Rites, which help the dying to join the Lord. In order to bring this action to life on earth, John the Baptist was there to set an example of purification through the water of Baptism. Jesus was also baptized, as a testimony to the importance of this act, which became one of the seven sacraments of the Catholic Church. Through the action of John the Baptist, God's grace touches mankind, and this grace is passed on through faith.

John the Baptist is therefore the one who prepared the way for Jesus, becoming the Saviour. Like the pagan religions that preceded it, the Christian religion draws on solar symbolism, which is found in many aspects of Christian celebrations. Similarly, for Freemasonry, is not the Sun a radiant celestial body, providing light and warmth? For the Church, this light is divine.

Saint John the Baptist is the last prophet of the Old Testament who announces the coming of Jesus, the Son of God. With his announcement, he closes the Old Covenant (Old Testament) and announces the arrival of the Kingdom of God by performing baptisms in the River Jordan.

In Christian esoteric symbolism, the summer solstice celebrates the height of divine light, with a rapidly declining cycle after the announcement of the coming of the Kingdom of God. It is in a way a call to man to follow the Lord. This call opens the door to the "little mysteries" accessible to men who have faith.

On the other hand, the Feast of Saint John the Evangelist, represented by Saint John the Evangelist, after the darkness and cold surrounding nature give way to night and day, through the Light. Thus, the winter solstice is a time of hope for Christians, because the solstice heralds, on the one hand, the regeneration of Mother Nature and, on the other hand, a new era. The Church's appropriation of the solstice festivals, including sacred elements and a double festival of light, became a powerful tool for conversion. This power of conversion is accompanied by joy and gladness. Did not John the Baptist say the following:

"He (the Messiah) must increase, but I must decrease."

This is a beautiful Christian image of cycles, involving divine light. The winter Saint John's Day opens the door to the gods and thus represents the "Great Mysteries" beyond human understanding.

At the end of the 17th century, Jacques-Bénigne Bossuet (Bishop of Maux) Christianized the summer solstice. This meant that, following this Christianization, the fires lit during the solstice celebrations became the fires of Saint John's Day. Gradually, the Church banned superstitions.

John the Evangelist offers a unique vision focused on knowledge and light. He highlights the profound meaning of Jesus' words. Unlike the other evangelists (Matthew, Mark, Luke), he begins with a prologue that sets him apart from the other Apostles. As a reminder, the Prologue begins as follows:

1 In the beginning was the Word*; and the Word was with God; and the Word was God.

2 It* was in the beginning with God.

3 All things were made through it, and without it nothing was made that has made.

4 In it was [the] life, and the life was the light of men*.

5 And the light shines in the darkness, and the darkness did not comprehend it.

It should be noted that in Freemasonry, in the Ancient and Accepted Scottish Rite, at one point in the ritual, the Worshipful Master says the following:

"The light shines in the darkness, but the darkness has not understood it."

Other pagan festivals have been Christianized, such as All Saints' Day (All Souls' Day). The Babylonians celebrated the dead every month and priests offered sacrifices (Funk & Wagnalls Standard, 1949). The same was true of the Greeks and Romans, who organized festivals in honour of the dead.

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4. The links between the four symbols and the four elements with "V.I.T.R.I.O.L."

The solstice festival marks the transition from Darkness to Light and from Light to Darkness. In Freemasonry, there are four symbols:

Light – Nature – Brotherhood – Knowledge

Then we discover the four elements:

Earth – Water – Air – Fire

What connection can we establish between the four symbols, the four elements and V.I.T.R.I.O.L.? Here is a quick explanation.

Being free in the 21st century means being free from passions, addictions, beliefs, not being a prisoner of one's certainties, etc. (a completely different perception from three hundred years ago).

Being honest in the 21st century: honesty implies righteousness of mind and behavior, respecting others, and observing the rights and duties of justice. It is a concept linked to integrity and honesty. At this level, as our Civil Code is based on the Napoleonic Code, there has ultimately been no major change, with the legislative framework remaining more rigid.

Being of good character in the 21st century: implies a person's moral sense, conduct, and customs in accordance with morality and ethics. It is the opposite of deception, cheating, or theft. It is at this level, which is more fluid and less defined, that perceptions have changed.

Light is linked to Fire: the fires of St. John's Day, but also to Air, because fire needs oxygen. Light is indirectly linked to Water, because for the Earth to be fertile, it needs Fire (heat) and Water.

Nature also needs the four elements to live and produce. Brotherhood is also linked to the four elements, because we are all part of the macrocosm and we are microcosms living on Earth, needing water, air and heat. Added to this is human warmth or love, since we are social beings.

Knowledge is connected to everything else, because knowledge allows us to understand the interactions and relationships between Light, Nature, Earth, Water, Air and Fire.

As for the interactions between Knowledge and Brotherhood: knowing how to be brotherly requires knowledge of oneself and others, in order to be both cautious and confident. It is about knowledge of human beings, their qualities and their faults.

And what about VITRIOL in all this? Vitriol invites us to introspection, which requires self-knowledge before we can hope to know others. For Vitriol is the Latin acronym for "Visita Interiora Terrae Rectificando Invenies Occultam Lapidem", which means

"Visit the interior of the Earth and by rectifying, you will find the hidden stone". It is through introspection and observation, but also by sharing in fraternal Agapes and sharing knowledge, that the Mason will be able to understand the links between the elements and symbols.

5. The symbols, elements and "V.I.T.R.I.O.L." with three essential requirements for entering Freemasonry: "Free, Honest and of Good Morals".

When the profane knocks on the door of the Temple, he is placed in the Chamber of Reflection (or Cavern) by the Expert brother. In the Chamber of Reflection, he encounters the element "Earth". Then, after knocking on the door of the Lodge, he must pass through the low door, blindfolded and presented "neither naked nor clothed" (REAA) and undergo three other "journeys" during which he will experience the elements "Water, Air and Fire" before he can receive the Light. It is worth noting that beyond the many possible interpretations of the symbolism of the four elements, there is a little-known common thread linking these three elements: purification.

Water purifies through washing, air purifies the atmosphere, and fire purifies through its flame. The inscription VITRIOL invites him to introspection, as he sees a skull, a rooster, and other alchemical elements, as well as other inscriptions.

He wrote his philosophical testament in good conscience, by the light of a burning candle.

The solstice also has elements that symbolize the values that Freemasonry attaches to St John's Day:

- The bonfires of Saint John's Day symbolize light.
- Nature, which is changing and is honoured with elements such as grain, wine, oil and incense

- Brotherhood and a reminder of the obligations of a Mason
- Knowledge, the cornerstone of Freemasonry, which will be discussed further below.

The three imperatives (or qualities) required to enter Freemasonry are prerequisites:

- To be free
- Be honest
- Be of good character

To be free: to be free from passions, addictions, beliefs, not to be a prisoner of one's convictions, etc.

Being honest: honesty implies righteousness of mind and behaviour, respect for others, observance of the rights and duties of justice; it is a concept linked to integrity and honesty.

Being of good character: implies a person's moral sense, conduct, customs and habits in accordance with morality and ethics. It is the opposite of deception, cheating or theft.

Links between these imperatives or qualities and the four symbols and four elements:

A profane person who does not possess these three qualities will be rejected by the Lodge where he seeks admission. Why?

Because he will not be able to 'die symbolically' and be reborn by making his three journeys, during which he will have to undergo 'purification'. Already in the Cabinet of Reflection, how could he engage in soul-searching and, in all conscience, write his philosophical testament?

Regarding the four symbolic elements (Light – Nature – Brotherhood – Knowledge), how could he understand the oaths and ideas, respect them and evolve towards the Light, when he is ultimately not recommended? Furthermore, the three qualities are necessary to have another necessary quality: to be faithful.

In the English Scottish Rite, at the Closing of the Lodge, the Brothers strike their hearts with their fists and say three times: "Fidelity! Fidelity! Fidelity!", marking an essential quality in Freemasonry.

6. Reflections on Knowledge and Virtues

The Church has a religion based on dogma. Followers must believe without any real proof, and believing is already a blessing: this is the **Christian faith**. The Church says that "God is Love" and that he sent his Son, the Redeemer, to save our souls; crucified on the cross, he rose again three days later. He shed his blood for us, and the Protestant Church validates Baptism, referring to John the Baptist who baptized Jesus in the River Jordan. This act is therefore an example to follow in order to symbolically wash away man's sins. It is Divine

grace linked to **Christian hope**. Finally, **Christian charity** is linked to love of neighbour: this is the third theological virtue.

For a religious person, **knowledge** is closely linked to knowledge of the Scriptures, which is of a 'major' nature, whereas knowledge not related to faith is of a human nature and therefore 'minor'.

Unlike the position of the Church, which is built on dogma, Freemasonry is non-dogmatic, even though its foundations are also based on theological virtues, as well as cardinal virtues. With regard to theological virtues, Freemasons therefore have a different view from religious people. For Freemasons, **knowledge** is the cornerstone that enables them to have a different view of theological virtues; this is what makes Freemasonry "adogmatic" (no dogmatic).

Masonic faith is linked to perfectibility and knowledge, which is itself linked to the Mason's duty to seek the indescribable and ineffable Light. For Masons, the light is therefore within us and we must seek it within ourselves. The Mason's faith is to believe that "Alone we can do nothing, but together we can do everything" (REAA rite).

Knowledge is of the "Major" type for the Mason. Knowledge is itself linked to the faith of the Mason, whose quest is to seek the Truth, knowing that no one possesses it (the Unattainable Star). This truth is connoted with Knowledge, which implies a relentless and infinite search. As a result, man is free to think, to introspect and to assess, but without judging, as dogma implies judgement. The faith of the Mason is the belief that nothing is impossible, that one must work tirelessly on oneself, "conquer one's passions" in order to progress on one's Masonic journey.

Masonic Hope is linked to this quest for perfectibility, in order to improve ourselves. While Hope is linked to the construction of the inner Temple, it is also linked to the construction of the outer Temple: the Brothers, mankind, in order to build a better world. From this point of view, Freemasonry has a "globalist" vision of the world.

As for Masonic charity, it is linked to the following concepts: "Freedom, Equality, Fraternity". Freedom from beliefs, freedom from certainties, freedom from our inclinations, but also the freedom to give, the freedom to make choices and to take responsibility for them. Equality is linked to equality between Brothers and between men (men and women, of course), equality linked to Justice, but also linked to the cardinal virtues, such as temperance and prudence. Fraternity is linked to brotherly spirit and brotherly love, also tying in with the idea of helping one's neighbour.

Knowledge involves a great deal of reflection in the life of a Mason. He must constantly think about the alchemists: V.I.T.R.I.O.L. This can be done through introspection and self-examination. Without wishing to be exhaustive, here are a few points for reflection on Knowledge. We can find links between them:

- Knowledge and self-knowledge in relation to brotherly love
- Knowledge of Masonic values and their preservation by each individual
- Knowledge in relation to the practice of introspection
- Knowledge in relation to the Royal Art
- Knowledge in relation to spiritual development
- Knowledge of the important concept of fraternal sharing
- Knowledge of our inclinations, beliefs and convictions
- Knowledge in relation to Masonic landmarks and rules
- Knowledge of the oaths taken
- Knowledge about our commitments
- Knowledge about our doubts
- Knowledge of our sincere desire to progress
- Knowledge of oneself (I), knowledge of others (you) in order to arrive at shared knowledge (we).

I will conclude by asking myself the following question:

Doesn't a lot of water have to flow over the pebbles to smooth out their rough edges so that each pebble becomes rounded and smooth? Aren't we the pebbles?

And so, who is the water?

6.1 Solstice song (without score)

I looked at the past
 And in the darkness
 Light shines

It is only a passage
 A new message

The old Janus is dead
 The young Janus is here
 And I contemplate the future

It's just a passing phase
A new message

The lights are going out
And the light fades
Once again, it is dark

It's just a passing phase
A new message

7. Conclusion

I will conclude with these words: this work is only a beginning and not an end, because we must keep searching, and when we find something, we suddenly realize that what we have found is neither complete nor final. What we have found is only a stepping stone, an indicator or a guide that allows us to go even further. Knowledge, you said?

8. Reference rituals and readings

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